

IMPROVING THE QUALITY ASSESSMENT OF INVESTMENT PROJECTS IN A FAST-CHANGING ENVIRONMENT

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Annotation. The article examines the content, nature, features, functions and role of investments in economic development. Macro and micro economic functions of investments are classified and described. The need to classify the functions of investments at the public, economic and private levels is justified. The role of investments in fixed assets in the development of the manufacturing and processing industries was assessed, the dynamics of investments in fixed assets was analyzed. We studied the share of investments in fixed assets through centralized and decentralized sources of financing and considered investment projects implemented in our country at the expense of these funds. Based on the results of the study, general conclusions were formed and recommendations were developed aimed at attracting and effectively mastering investments in fixed assets.

Keywords: investments, investment projects, fixed assets, functions, intensive development, manufacturing industry, financing, centralized funds, decentralized funds, investment activities, foreign investment, investment climate, gross domestic product, modernization, investment resources, tangible values, intangible values, risks.

Introduction

World practice shows that the development of a country's economy through investments contributes to intensive development. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan noted, "Any state that has pursued an active investment policy has achieved stable growth of its economy. Therefore, it is no exaggeration to say that investment is the driver of the economy, or, in Uzbek terms, the heart of the economy" .

In recent years, Uzbekistan has adopted a number of legislative acts and set priority tasks to increase investment activity, actively attract and effectively absorb foreign direct investment, implement investment projects within the framework of public-private partnerships, and modernize fixed capital. In particular, in order to increase the investment attractiveness of our country, increase the volume of foreign direct investment, and accelerate the transformation processes of large companies and commercial banks with a predominant state share, while introducing modern corporate governance mechanisms, the "National Investment Fund of the Republic of Uzbekistan" was established. The main task of this Fund is to place the Fund's shares

on leading foreign stock exchanges and to participate in the processes of attracting investments in the Fund's assets and their privatization.

The high probability of unfavorable development of innovative investment enterprises requires expanding sources of financial resources. It is necessary to evaluate investment projects and consider investment flows in general, taking into account modern trends caused by various negative factors. Regarding the first, it should be noted that although it is problematic to assess the quality of investment projects, it is important to bring the assessment results to a reasonable level.

However, the lack of financial resources, fierce competition in the global capital market necessitate the development of specific state innovation and investment programs that would most effectively accumulate and use available financial resources to protect the country's economy from various shocks, primarily the impact of the coronavirus pandemic.

To develop state programs that lead to effective results, while having effective mechanisms of financial control and management in the changing conditions of their implementation, modeling methods are widely used in world practice, with which you can determine the optimal value of economic stimulus instruments of investment policy. At the same time, despite the general similarity of the principles of modeling investment and economic programs, their goals are different. The goal of state investment policy is social security, and the task of this investment policy is to increase production efficiency.

It should be noted that the absence of a clear model of state regulation of the investment market leads to a weakening of economic development. This significantly reduces the effectiveness of investment policy and makes it dependent on the interests of investors who can influence government decisions. The costs can be very high. The model of state investment policy makes it possible to identify the necessary and sufficient conditions for ensuring the continuous positive development of the country's economy until 2035. Stimulation should be carried out within a narrow "corridor" of corrective management decisions that respond to changes in the socio-economic situation both in the country and in the world. At the same time, ineffective spending and their negative impact can be minimized.

Modeling investment programs in Uzbekistan is associated with limited financial resources, in particular, with the prevention of risk factors caused by the coronavirus pandemic, which forces the state policy in this area to focus on more effective and rapid compensation measures. At the same time, investment activity is determined by the factors that shape the investment market. Among them, the general demand for investment flows occupies a special place, the essence of which lies in the varying degrees of attractiveness, reliability and economic feasibility of the areas of their use.

The demand for investment resources, of course, should include an assessment of all their potential consumers and investment objects, the selection of rational and promising investment projects. The practice of selecting attractive investment objects and forming investment programs has shown the importance of demand and the development of methods for its assessment.

To determine the real need for investment capital, you need to consider the economically justified. The main characteristic of the qualified requirement is an investment project, which, in addition to a business plan, consists of qualitative and quantitative parameters. The latter is assessed depending on the level of modernization, development of the territory, production and social infrastructure. Several indicators can be used for this. One of them is the indicator of the distribution of investment volumes by regions and years. At the same time, it characterizes only the investment activity of the investment market of the region in comparison with the average indicator for a given year. In addition, quantitative parameters can be determined using the indicator of the saturation of the region with investment - the level of concentration of investment capital, as well as the volume of investments accumulated per unit of area or per person of a given region over a certain period. The measure of these volumes is the gross fixed capital formation. Other similar measures (for example, gross national product, state budget revenues, household deposits and foreign investments) are of secondary importance compared to the volume of accumulated investment capital and the population, although, if they are correctly taken into account, these indicators can increase the accuracy of the calculations.

The indicator of the level of concentration of investment capital in terms of content is close to the indicator of its actual gross capital formation, which includes the costs of acquiring and improving land, buildings, machinery and equipment. The volume of investments characterizes the scale of investment processes, which are directly related not only to investment objects, but also to the presence or absence of human resources and appropriate infrastructure necessary for their implementation.

The methodology for determining the quality of concentrated investment capital is developed on the basis of an assessment of the production cycles of enterprises and an analysis of the existing costs of operation. This method is often used to study the "investment attractiveness" of enterprises.

Taking into account the cycle of the enterprise, depicted in Diagram 1, within the framework of its activities, it is possible to create a model of the movement of resources. However, the movement of resources does not clearly show how much investment capital plays in its activities. However, before revealing the place of investment capital, we decided to explain the movement of funds using mathematical tools and show the movement of funds.

You can use the category of investment demand. This is an analogue of the effective demand for goods, only in the first case it is provided for money, and in return for it an investment product is provided. To obtain resources, the recipient forms a scientifically and economically justified offer, the implementation of which allows the investor to receive capital gains from the invested funds.

In any case, the process associated with the release of innovative products contributes to profitable work, i.e. means making a profit from the production of products.

Keynes envisaged the possibility of obtaining a negative value of the latter under the following conditions: during the specified period, production costs increase, while the increase in the volume of products does not end and it is not sold. This can also happen when the integration processes in the industry are so far advanced that entrepreneurs produce a large part of the equipment they need, and the overall indicators are characterized by specific investments.

This statement is also justified in relation to the current situation of science-intensive enterprises, which, in the conditions of a decrease in product sales, are unable to compensate for the sharp increase in production costs. At the same time, their main products are mainly science-intensive technologies and scientific developments used for their own needs, that is, enterprises produce their own means of production, in fact, invest "in themselves". This reduces the investment attractiveness of these enterprises and leads to negative operating costs, since the amount of investment costs ($\downarrow \uparrow \text{З_ат}^{\text{ИНВ}} 1$) increases by a corresponding amount. It follows that an enterprise at stage 7, all other things being equal, has the maximum investment risk and the greatest development potential.

Figure 2. Investments in fixed assets, trillion soums

Source: Compiled based on statistical data from the Statistical Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan (4.INVESTMENT AND CONSTRUCTION WORKS (1).pdf.).

During the analyzed period, investments in fixed assets had a steady growth trend. Because such dynamics are observed in all intervening years. This situation is positive from the point of view of modernization and further development of production sectors, in particular, manufacturing industry, mining industry, electricity, gas supply, housing construction, agriculture. However, today there are serious problems associated with the effective development of industry. The main of them is “the high level of physical obsolescence of fixed assets (on average 50%)”.

This, in turn, negatively affects the competitiveness of manufactured products. At the same time, this situation leads to a decrease in the level of competitiveness of industrial enterprises, inefficient use of material and raw material resources. In this regard, the establishment of the task of ensuring an average annual growth of investments in fixed capital of about 7 percent in the "Uzbekistan-2030" strategy requires a further increase in the volume of investments in fixed capital and the modernization of fixed assets. In turn, the growth of GDP creates a favorable and reliable environment for attracting investments in the renewal, technical re-equipment, and modernization of fixed capital.

The share of investments in fixed capital financed from centralized sources of financing in the total volume of investments amounted to 12.7 percent in 2023, which decreased by 14.8 percentage points compared to 2019, while 87.3 percent of total investments in fixed capital were absorbed from decentralized sources of financing, which increased by 14.8 percentage points compared to 2019 (Figure 3).

During the 4th stage, as a rule, the majority of funds for fixed capital come from direct investments, and if the company does not have its own growth potential, as well as from portfolio and loans, if it has its own investment potential and appropriate development prospects.

Analysis has shown that the duration of the 4th stage is different for raw material and innovative enterprises. This is because for raw material enterprises it is usually determined by the time of development of deposits and can last several decades; in cases requiring science, the period for the development of a particular product model is from 2 to 5 years. Despite the longer raw material cycle, the innovative production cycle is a more efficient system compared to the enterprises of the raw material industry, since at each subsequent stage of development the amount of operating costs ($\downarrow \uparrow \Sigma_{\text{ат}^{\text{ИНВ}} 2}$) is added to the amount of accumulated profit ($\downarrow \uparrow \Sigma_{\text{ат}^{\text{ИНВ}} 3}$). It is this process that ensures technical progress. In the commodity industry, such a combination is almost absent, since the mine closure eliminates a large part of the operating cost. This process is presented in Figure 2.

The duration of the first stage (1 and 1 •) in innovative enterprises is not the same. In the first stage (1), innovators have a flatter curve, which is explained by the additional costs and time spent on advertising their products and capturing a share of the market. This can take many years and often requires a large amount of money compared to investment in fixed assets (for example, advertising of goods). For raw material enterprises, on the contrary, in the first stage (1 •) the graph curve slopes sharply upwards, since their competitively priced products have a stable demand from the first day of production.

It should be noted that in the second stage (2 and 2 •) the volume of production becomes more innovative (or scientifically intensive), the enterprise begins to grow rapidly and “explode” in a short time, after which it quickly becomes obsolete and a new stage of development begins. In raw material enterprises, the opposite is true: in the second stage, the graph curve becomes almost horizontal and continues until the raw material extraction site is closed.

Scheme 2 shows how the accumulation of operating costs ($Z_{at}^{inv 3}$), which ensures the overall growth of income, occurs. In addition, with expanded repetitive production, part of the enterprise's profit is reinvested in other facilities. However, only money is reinvested in the raw material sector, and in more innovative (or knowledge-intensive) enterprises, part of the operating costs are recovered. This word can be compared to the well-known logical formula: "If two people exchange apples, each of them will have an apple; if two people exchange ideas, each of them will have two ideas." indicates its dependence on its own characteristics.

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